

POST CONSOLIDATION DETERMINANTS OF BANK PROFITABILITY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined bank specific, industry specific and economic determinants of bank profitability in Nigeria. The study ascertained the determinants of bank profitability with particular focus on the post banking consolidation reforms period. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was employed on a balanced panel of 13 DMBs from 2006 to 2018. The results showed a positive and significant relationship between the three proxies of profitability (ROA, ROE, and NIM) and capital base, bank size, liquidity, operational efficiency, and market concentration. Whereas, the proxies of profitability have a negative relationship with credit risk. Additionally, the relationship between cyclical output and profitability (ROA & ROE) was found to be significant and negative, while the relationship between NIM and cyclical output was found to be positive but insignificant. However, no relationship was found between inflation and bank profitability in Nigeria.

Keywords – Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Net Interest Margin (NIM), Capital Base, Bank Size, Liquidity, Operational Efficiency, Market Concentration, Cyclical Output, Inflation.

INTRODUCTION

The banking industry is one of the significant sectors of the financial system in most countries (San & Heng, 2013). A strong banking industry is important in every country and can have a significant effect in supporting economic development through efficient financial services. Banks plays a crucial role of promoting the growth of economy by mobilizing savings and using the mobilized savings in financing the most productive sectors of economic (Alkhazaleh & Almsafir, 2014). Hence, banking institutions are crucial for the stability and development of any country's financial system because of the important role they play in the allocation of financial resources to different sectors of the economy (Rani & Zergaw, 2017; Moussa & Hdidar, 2019). Governments role out economic and monitory policies to manage inflation, encourage

spending or savings through commercial banks. In the whole, the economy generally performs better when banking institutions are profitable and operating efficiently (Kutum, 2017).

The financial strength of a banking institution is unquestionably associated to its profitability, thus, the most important need of any bank's management and leadership is to make profits on a continuous basis since this will guarantee the bank's continuous existence. As such, achieving profitability is vital to any bank (Adeusi, Kolapo & Aluko, 2014). The importance of bank profitability at both the micro and macro levels has made researchers, academics, bank managements and bank regulatory authorities to develop considerable interest on the factors that determine bank profitability (Athanasoglou, Panayiotis, Brissimis, Sophocles, Delis & Matthaios, 2005). To that end, this study seeks to ascertain bank specific factors, industry related factors and the macroeconomic indicators of bank profitability. The bank specific factors consist of the capital base, liquidity, bank size, operational efficiency and credit risk; while market concentration fall under the industry related category and inflation and cyclical output for the macro-economic factors.

Statement of the Problem

Given the increased pressure of globalization, deregulation, parallel competition from the non-banking financial institutions and volatile market dynamics, core banking institutions constantly seek ways to remain profitable.

Profitable banks can diversify their business, effectively hedge against adverse effects, and reward their stakeholders in several ways. Hence, understanding and regularly updating knowledge regarding the determinants of banking profitability is very important to guarantee financial stability (Islam, 2016; Rani & Zergaw, 2017).

To be specific, the banking sector in Nigeria has in the past two decades gone through numerous structural changes (2005 Banking Consolidation Reforms and 2009 Banking Reforms) which has affected the banking industry in particular and the economy as whole. In addition to the two banking reforms, the banking sector went through several mergers, acquisitions, the adoption of resolution measures in the form of bridge banking mechanisms, in addition to government bailouts.

The above gives credence to the motivation for this study and adds to the existing literature of country specific studies that have examined the significance of both banks specific, industry related and macroeconomic variables as determinants of bank profits in Nigeria. The aim of this study is to ascertain the bank specific, industry specific and economic determinants of bank profitability in Nigeria from 2006 to 2018.

Research Questions

1. How have bank specific variables and industry related factors (capital base, liquidity, bank size, operational efficiency, credit risk, and market concentration) impacted the profitability of Nigerian deposit money banks?

2. How have economic indicators (inflation and cyclical output) impacted the profitability of Nigerian deposit money banks?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Bank Profitability

The term “profitability” denotes the capacity of business entities to maintain their profit year after year. The profitability of banking institutions indicates the success of the management and it is one of the most important performance indicators for the investors. Positive changes in the performance of banking institutions contributes to economic progress, as profits influence the investment and savings decisions of companies. This is because a rise in profits improves the cash flow position of companies and offers greater flexibility (i.e. through retained earnings). Easier access to finance facilities greater investments which improve productivity, competitiveness and employment (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2015).

Return on Assets (ROA)

Business entities make investments in assets (for instance, buildings, equipment, machinery, etc.) to generate a return. Business entities want to make sure that they maximize the income they generate from the assets they own. ROA assesses a company’s profitability relative to the assets it controls, thus it is a measure of how efficiently it is using the assets at its disposal. If ROA is low, it indicates that income has been low compared to the amount of assets owned (Marr, 2012).

Return on Equity (ROE)

ROE measures how much profit a company is generating from the money the shareholders have invested. Businesses with a high ROE (especially if they have little or no debt) are able to grow without large capital expenditures which in turn allows managers to reinvest the capital to improve business operations without the owners of the business (shareholders) having to invest more capital. A high ROE means that there is less of a need to take on debt and borrow money elsewhere (Marr, 2012).

Net Interest (NIM)

NIM could be considered as a useful tool for tracking the profitability of banking investing and lending activities over a specific period of time as it mirrors the interest rate spread between loans and deposits, in addition to transaction costs as well as taxes that are borne directly to borrowers and savers. Thus, we could view the NIM as an indicator of efficiency and profitability of the banking system (Demirguc-Kunt & Huizinga, 1999). Though the NIM represents a vital component of profitability and summarises the bank net interest rate of return, it only focuses on the core activity of banks and does not include other revenue from services, such as fees and other non-interest income, and non-interest expenses (Hijazeen, 2017).

Bank Specific Determinants of Profitability

Capital Base

Capital adequacy is a measure of the amount of a bank's capital expressed as a percentage of its risk weighed credit exposures (Reserve Bank of New Zealand, 2004). The Basel Accords since 1988 have proposed that banks possess adequate capital in order to ensure that they are able to absorb losses and function in difficult times. Applying minimum capital adequacy ratios promotes the stability and efficiency of financial system by reducing the likelihood of banks becoming insolvent.

The high level of bank capital boosts the confidence and trust of the public about the soundness of the bank. Stronger banks can channelize available funds in business activities and make high profits (Pasaribu and Sari, 2011). The relationship between bank capital and profitability in banking has been investigated by several researchers. For example, Ozili (2017) opines that regulatory bank capital has a positive impact on the profitability of commercial banks in Africa. Berger and Bouwman (2013) assert that bank capital influences the performance of small banks in that it enables them to survive. It also improves the performance of large and medium banks, particularly in a crisis period. Islam and Nishiyama (2016) suggested that equity capital has a positive impact on the profitability of South Asian commercial banks. Tran, Lin & Nguyen (2016) concluded that capital and performance do not have a linear relationship. They document an inverse relationship in capital and profitability of larger banks and a positive relationship in smaller banks. Lee and Hsieh (2013), state that capital and profitability of commercial banks in Asian countries have a positive relationship.

Liquidity

Maness & Zietlow (2005) summarizes three components to define liquidity, which is amount, time and cost. Amount means how many resources the company has to fulfil its financial obligations; time means how long the company takes to transfer assets into cash; cost means if the company can transfer assets into cash without much costs. For the banking industry, liquidity is defined as "the capability to secure the necessary funding through attracting deposits, cash, or pledging encumbered assets" (Aldo, 2015).

The last global financial crises highlighted just how important a role liquidity can play in the operations of banks. The impact is not just on operations but there is also a direct bearing on the profitability (Lamberg et al., 2009). Banks should strive to maintain the right balance of liquidity in order to avoid short-term liquidity pressures.

Raykov (2017), conducted a study on the trade-off between liquidity and profitability in Bulgaria with also the financial crisis underpinning the study. The empirical findings of this research showed negative correlation between liquidity and profitability. Ibrahim (2017), analysed the impact of liquidity on profitability in Iraqi banks and observed that there was a positive correlation between liquidity and profitability. Tran et al. (2016) assessed the relationship between liquidity creation and bank profitability of US banks. They found that

highly liquid banks which exhibited high illiquid risk tend to have lower profitability, while banks who create higher liquidity earn lower profits. Islam and Nishiyama (2016) document that liquidity, as measured by total loans to total deposit ratio, has a positive impact on profitability in case of net interest margin, but this relationship is insignificant.

Bank Size

The size of a business means the ability it possesses and the variety and number of production capability or the quantity and multiplicity of services the business can be offered concomitantly to its customers. In a simpler way, the best indication of “bigness” of a firm is the size of its management group or the amount of assets it possesses compared to others in the same industry (Sritharan, 2015).

Banks have good reasons to believe profitability and size are related. Increasing bank size can increase bank profitability by allowing banks to realize economies of scale. For example, increasing size allows banks to spread fixed costs over a greater asset base, thereby reducing their average costs. Increasing banks’ asset size can also reduce risk by diversifying operations across product lines, sectors, and regions (Mester, 2010).

Operational Efficiency

Poor expenses management is the main contributors to poor profitability (Sufian and Chong 2008). In bank performance literature, operational expense efficiency is usually used to assess managerial efficiency in banks. Although the relationship between expenditure and profits appears straightforward implying that higher expenses mean lower profits and the opposite, this may not always be the case. The reason is that higher amounts of expenses may be associated with higher volume of banking activities and therefore higher revenues. In relatively uncompetitive markets where banks enjoy market power, costs are passed on to customers; hence there would be a positive correlation between overheads costs and profitability (Flamini *et al*, 2009). Naceur (2003) found a positive and significant impact of overheads costs to profitability indicating that such costs are passed on to depositors and lenders in terms of lower deposits rates or higher lending rates.

Credit risk

A bank exists not only to accept deposits but also to grant credit facilities, therefore inevitably exposed to credit risk. (Kolapo, Ayeni&Oke, 2012)

According to the European Central Bank (2016), “a bank loan is considered non-performing when more than 90 days pass without the borrower paying the agreed instalments or interest. Non-performing loans are also called bad debt.” A loan which performs will bring in projected revenues and provide the funds needed to lend to other borrowers. When borrowers default, banks have to stretch their capitals to raise funds to give loans to prospective borrowers. If it fails to raise new funds to loan out, the bank’s capacity to generate revenue through interest on

loans also reduces. Any bank which finds itself in a situation like that will struggle to compete and survive in the long term.

Saeed & Zahid (2016) findings were firm on credit risk having a positive relationship with profitability. In Bangladesh, Noman, et al. (2015), revealed that prudent credit measures were key contributors to profitability. Also Djan, (2015) revealed credit risk having significant impact on a bank's profitability. Abiola & Olausi (2014) findings revealed that credit risk had a significant impact on profitability of banks. Akonga'a (2014) revealed that financial risk had significant impact on the financial performance of commercial banks. Kargi (2011) found that credit risk management has a significant impact on the profitability of Nigerian banks. Kithinji (2010), conducted a study to assess the impact of credit risk on profitability using commercial banks in Kenya. The study resulted in a neutral impact from credit risk on profitability. A study conducted by Hosna, Manzura & Juanjuan, (2009) on four commercial banks in Sweden, for the 2000 to 2008 financial year, revealed a positive correlation between credit risk and profitability.

Industry Specific Determinant

Market concentration

Concentration in banking industry means the concentration of funds in a small number of large and major banks. It is a situation when major banks, which play a decisive role, in one or another way, prevail in smaller banks. Being developed by the same laws as the concentration of industry, it inevitably leads to monopoly (Staroselskaja 2011). It has also been argued that, the higher the concentration in the local banking market, the higher the prices are for financial services and consequently the higher the banks' profits (Ravenscraft, 1982) and (Jimenez et al 2007). During competition, many smaller banks go bankrupt and simply cease to exist. Other smaller banks formally retain their independence, in fact, obeying the power of the larger ones (Bikker, & Haaf 2002). The concentration of bank capital is primarily based on the centralization of production: large industrial companies usually put and keep their available cash capitals in large banks, which strengthens their positions and contributes to the displacement of small banks. The concentration of bank capital leads to the competition in banking industry where large banks have a decisive advantage over smaller ones (Staroselskaja 2011) the majority of which are included in the sphere of influence of big banks and eventually lose its independence thus becoming the prime offices or branches of the larger ones. Ideally, the evaluation of competitive conditions and the degree of concentration in banking industry should begin by rigorously defining the market under consideration. Predictions about the economic theory for the role of bank size and national concentration are mixed. According to the "concentration-stability" view, a concentrated banking system with a few large institutions is more stable because the banks may be more profitable, better diversified and easier to monitor, and therefore more resilient to shocks. In contrast, the "concentration-fragility" view predicts less stability from high concentration and a few large institutions because these institutions may be likely to take on more risk due to implicit "too big to fail" policies or preferences with regard to the risk-expected return trade-off (Berger, Levine, Haubrich & Dermiguc-Kunt, 2004).

Economic Determinants of Profitability

Inflation

Inflation has important effects on banks under different aspects. First, the bank lending is influenced by inflation. According to Boyd and Champ (2006), some economists suggest that countries with higher inflation normally have small banking and equity market, the amount of loan made by banks decreases through ration credit especially to private sector. Second, the profitability is also affected by inflation.

Oleka, Eyisi&Onyeze (2014)results revealed that there is positive but not significant relationship between inflation and the investment decision proxy by lending volume of commercial banks operating in Nigeria. This implies that the impact of inflation on investment decision for all the Nigerian commercial banks was positive but not statistically significant. To this end, investment decisions within the profitability position of Nigerian banks have no direct relationship with inflation within the period under review.

Cyclical Output

Economic activity, which is measured by the growth rate or cyclical component of GDP, is believed to influence bank profitability positively (Athanasoglou et al. 2006, Athanasoglou, Brissimis, & Delis, 2008; Dietrich & Wanzenried 2011; Flamini et al. 2009; Goddard et al. 2004; Trujillo-Ponce 2013; Davydenko 2010).

On one hand, positive relationship is expected because of the pro-cyclical nature of banking business (Athanasoglou et al., 2008; Chortareas, Garza-Garcia & Girardone, 2011). During boom period, banks in general expand lending and charge higher interest rate on loans as well as generate higher fee income through ever increased transactions in the stock market. Banks generate less bad assets (NPLs) and ultimately earn higher returns. On the other hand, Goddard et al., (2011) argue that abundance of business opportunities might lead to an intensification of competition and thus a negative relationship between GDP and profitability can be expected.

Empirical Review

Based on the literature, the existing studies on determinants of bank profitability can be broadly grouped into two.

The first stream of research work includes Flamini et al., Titko, Skvarciany & Jurevičienė, Petria et al., Djalilov and Piesse , Bourke , Short , Pasiouras and Kosmidou , Hsieh and Lee, Molyneux and Thornton, Naceur & Omran , Albertazzi and Gambacorta who focused on cross country data. For instance, Djalilov and Piesse, examined the factors that influence the level of bank profitability in transition economies particularly in Central and Eastern Europe between 2000 and 2013 for 275 banks using the generalized method of moments (GMM) technique. They found that credit risk positively and significantly determined bank profitability in the early transition but exhibited a negative impact in the late transition countries. The adverse

relationship was found between governance and bank profitability, and between monetary freedom and bank profitability only in late transition economies. In addition, better-capitalized banks were more profitable in early transition countries. However, Titko et al., conducted both multiple regression and correlation analyses to determine the drivers of bank profitability in Latvia and Lithuania from 2008 to 2014. Their findings indicated the absence of a significant link between net interest margin (measures profitability for Latvia), net commission and fees income as a percentage total assets (measure profitability for Lithuania), and independent variables. Petria et al., employed panel data to analyze the determinants of bank profitability in the European Union between 2004 and 2011 with the aid of fixed effect and random effect models. Their result showed that bank profitability (returns on average assets and returns on average equity) received significant influence from credit and liquidity risk, management efficiency, the diversification of business, the market concentration/competition, and economic growth.

The second stream include country specific studies, the studies presented below are examples. Hoffmann (2011) examined the determinants of the profitability of the US banks during the period 1995-2007. Using the GMM system estimator, the results showed a negative link between the capital ratio and the profitability, which supports the notion that banks are operating over-cautiously and ignoring potentially profitable trading opportunities. The analysis also records that economies of scale do not occur if one takes into consideration the size of the bank. Also, the results show that the exogenous factors determine the efficiency in the profitability of banks.

Vong& Chan (2009) examined the impact of bank characteristics as well as macroeconomic and financial structure variables on the performance of the Macao banking industry. They found asset quality, as measured by the loan-loss provisions and the loan-to-total assets ratio, to adversely affect the performance of banks. On the contrary, management efficiency as measured by the ratio of equity to total assets was positively related to banks performance. They concluded that, a bank's performance can be improved if it is well capitalized and borrows less to finance its operations. With regard to macroeconomic variables, only the rate of inflation exhibits a significant relationship with banks performance.

Naceur (2003) investigated the factors that affect Tunisian banks' profitability over the period 1980-2000. The results showed that, capital ratio, loans and stock market improvements have a positive relationship with profitability while the assets size found to have a negative relationship.

Alemu (2015) examined determinants of commercial banks profitability of eight banks in Ethiopia from for 10 years from 2002 - 2013. The study used multiple linear regressions and the fixed effect regression model to analyze data. The study established that size of banks; capital adequacy and gross domestic product have a positive and statistically significant relationship with bank profitability. While the study also revealed that liquidity risk, operational efficiency, funding cost and banking sector development have a negative and statistically significant

relation with profitability of banks. Finally, the study found that the relationship between efficiency of management, efficiency of employee, inflation and foreign exchange rate was statistically insignificant.

Nkegbe & Ustarz (2015) investigated banks performance in the Ghanaian banking industry for the period 2000-2010 using trend graphs, equations and panel data estimation techniques. They found liquidity, market share of loan and operational efficiency to be positively related to all the performance indicators. Non-performing loan is, however, significant and negatively related to only return on equity and return on assets. On the macroeconomic determinants, money supply is also negatively related to all the performance measures while gross domestic product though negatively related to all performance indicators, is only significant in the case of return on assets and net interest margins.

Utilising Nigerian banks, Iyoha and Ilaboya (2016) employed a panel research design, with bank specific and macroeconomic data covering the period 2006 to 2012. The data panel was analysed using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique. In conducting the estimation of bank specific and macro-economic characteristics and bank profit, the significant variables from fixed effect estimation of preliminary baseline regressions were extracted and regressed on PCAINDEX and TOBIN'S Q and the findings were: capital adequacy, economic stability, money supply, inflation rate, lending interest rate and exchange rate were statistically significant at 5% level of significance on PCAINDEX and TOBIN'S Q respectively.

Osuagwu (2014) showed that bank profitability is largely determined by credit risk and other factors that relate to the internal organization of banking firms. The study also revealed market concentration to be a significant determinant of bank profitability. More so, the study did not find evidence of structure-conduct-performance hypothesis, however empirical results show that there is no collusive behaviour amongst banks. Exchange rate is significant as a determinant of bank profitability through return on equity and non-interest margin, but not significant to return on asset as a measure of profitability.

Aremu et al, (2013) found that bank size and cost efficiency did not significantly determine bank profitability. However, credit risk and capital adequacy had a significant effect on bank profitability both in the long run and short run respectively. Also, while Liquidity affected bank profitability in the short run, labour efficiency only affected bank profitability in the long run. But as for the external or macroeconomic variables which determined bank profitability, only Broad Money Supply growth rate was found to be a significant driver both in the long run and in the short run.

METHODOLOGY

This study is an exploratory study, investigating the determinants of banks' profitability. It uses exploratory research which the goals are to discover new insights, ask questions and assess phenomena, in a different perspective (Adams & Schvaneveldt, 1991; Stebbins, 2001).

The study used secondary data collected from the financial statements of banks for a period of thirteen (13) years starting from 2006-2018. The data for the study was collected from the Annual reports of banks, the Nigerian stock exchange and the central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin.

A total of twenty-one deposit money banks (DMB) operate in the Nigerian banking sector however, only thirteen (13) DMBs with balanced data sets are used due to incomplete data as a result of mergers and acquisitions, absorptions and bridge banking.

Measurement of Study variables

Table 1

Variables used and measurement

Dependent Variables	Measurement
ROE	Net Income after Tax / Equity
ROA	Net Income after Tax / Total Asset
NIM	Net Profit after Tax / Turnover
Independent Variables	Measurement
Capital Base	Equity / Asset
Liquidity	Total Loans / Total asset
Bank Size	Natural Log of Total Asset
Operational Efficiency	Operating Cost / Gross Earnings
Credit Risk	Non Performing Loans / Total loans
Market Concentration	HHI index
Inflation	CPI
Cyclical Output	GDP growth rate

Model Specification

The regression model is written as:

$$P_{it} = \alpha + \sum_{b=1}^B \beta_b X_{it} + \sum_{s=1}^S \beta_s X_{it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

Where, P_{it} = profitability of bank I at time t, with $i=1 \dots N$ and $t=1 \dots T$ (dependent variable)

X_{it} = set of Independent variables

α = a constant term

$\beta_b, \beta_s, \beta_m$ = Coefficient for bank-specific, industry specific and macroeconomic determinants

ε_{it} = disturbance term

To measure the persistence of bank profits over time, we adopted the dynamic specification of the model in (1) where θ measures speed of adjustment to equilibrium and $\theta = [0, 1]$. The model in (1) is augmented as follows:

$$P_{it} = \alpha + \theta P_{it-1} + \sum_{b=1}^B \beta_b X_{it} + \sum_{s=1}^S \beta_s X_{it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(ii)$$

Where, P_{it} = profitability of bank I at time t, with $i=1 \dots N$ and $t=1 \dots T$ (dependent variable)

X_{it} = set of Independent variables

α = a constant term

$\beta_b, \beta_s, \beta_m$ = Coefficient for bank-specific, industry specific and macroeconomic determinants

ε_{it} = disturbance term

Model 1:

The functional form of this model can be written as:

$$ROA_{it} = f(CAB_{it}, LR_{it}, BS_{it}, OE_{it}, CR_{it}, MCON_{it}, INFL_{it}, CO_{it}) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

We can express this econometric model in a mathematical form as:

$$ROA_{it} = \kappa + \rho_i ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 CAB_{it} + \beta_2 LR_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 OE_{it} + \beta_5 CR_{it} + \beta_6 MCON_{it} + \beta_7 INFL_{it} + \beta_8 CO_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (1a)$$

Model 2:

The functional form of this model can be written as:

$$ROE_{it} = f(CAB_{it}, LR_{it}, BS_{it}, OE_{it}, CR_{it}, MCON_{it}, INFL_{it}, CO_{it}) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

We can express this econometric model in a mathematical form as:

$$ROE_{it} = \kappa + \rho_i ROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 CAB_{it} + \beta_2 LR_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 OE_{it} + \beta_5 CR_{it} + \beta_6 MCON_{it} + \beta_7 INFL_{it} + \beta_8 CO_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (2a)$$

Model 3:

The functional form of this model can be written as:

$$NIM_{it} = f(CAB_{it}, LR_{it}, BS_{it}, OE_{it}, CR_{it}, MCON_{it}, INFL_{it}, CO_{it}) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

We can express this econometric model in a mathematical form as:

$$NIM_{it} = \kappa + \rho_i NIM_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 CAB_{it} + \beta_2 LR_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 OE_{it} + \beta_5 CR_{it} + \beta_6 MCON_{it} + \beta_7 INFL_{it} + \beta_8 CO_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(3a)$$

Where; α = the constant term

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ = the regression parameters (i.e. coefficient of explanatory variables)

ROA = returns on assets

CAB = capital base

LR = liquidity risk

BS = bank size

OE = Operational Efficiency

CR = credit risk

MCON = market concentration

INFL = inflation

CO = cyclical output

i = cross-sectional dimension (ranges from 1 to N)

t = time series dimension (ranges from 1 to T)

ε_{it} = disturbance term

The study adopts the quantitative method of data analysis which entails the critical analysis and interpretation of figures and numbers, and attempts to find rationale behind the emergence of the main findings. The data collected was sorted for completeness and then analyzed using the ordinary least squares (OLS) statistical techniques.

RESULTS

Unit root test

Test for stationary nature of the variables was carried out using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The results of the unit root tests are presented in table 2. The result showed that all the variables are stationary at levels, and stationary at first difference. ADF Unit Root Test for Stationary levels at 5%.

$$Y_t = Dt + Z_t + e_t$$

Where,

D, = is the deterministic component (trend, seasonal component, etc.)

Z_t ~ is the stochastic component,

e_t = is the stationary error process.

Table 2

ADF Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Null Hypothesis: Variables has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=1 1)

	t-Statistic	Prob.¹
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	8.155220	001
Test critical values: 1% level	3.657411	
5% level	2.252170	
10% level	4.684471	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source; E-View 10.

Table 3

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: (Profit of Banks)

Method: Least Squares

Sample: 2006 - 2018

Included observations: 299 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Variables C	2.3145112	0.365211	9.364100	000
	14369521	11.36200	6.651410	001
S.E. of regression	635.2411	Akaike info criterion		10.32741
Sum squared resid	3652117.	Schwarz criterion		12.23700
Log likelihood	662.5431	Hannan-Quinn criter.		14.36210
Durbin-Watson stat	1.610			

Source: E-View 10 output.

When variables produce a stationary series, co-integration among them in the long run is feasible. Stationarity is obtained by comparing the test statistics with the critical value(s), if the test statistics is greater than the critical value numerically, the variable is stationary and if the reverse, it is non-stationary. The entire ADF statistics is greater than the critical value; hence, Stationarity exists among variables. As a result, data are adequate for further treatment and analysis since they are found to be stationary. To establish the existence of the long run relationship among variables, a co-integration test was performed using the Johansen's co-integration test.

Table 4
Johaasen Co-Integration Result

Hypothesized No. of CE'(s)	Eigen Value	Trace Statistics	b.05 Critical Value	Critical Prob**	Max-Eigen Statistics	Critical Value	Prob**
None*	1.32141	36.1210	36.2210	001	36.21110	11.62411	001
At most 1	0.12411	1.20065	4.741210	000	00021	2.247410	001

Max-eigen test indicate co-integrating equation at 5% level

Trace test indicates 1 co-integrating equation (s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

Source Compiled from E-View 10.

Johansen's Co-integration test confirmed that a long run relationship exists between the study variables variables.

Table 5

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.115505	0.018343	6.297114	0.0000
CAPITAL_BASE	0.057279	0.029134	1.966074	0.0403
LIQUITY	0.061289	0.054704	1.120379	0.2636
BANK_SIZE	0.064682	0.027298	2.369491	0.0185
OPERATIONAL_EFFICIENC Y	0.009899	0.003447	2.871604	0.0044
CREDIT_RISK	-0.001353	0.001480	-0.914010	0.3615
MARKET_CONCENTRATI ON	0.324141	2.321-05	1.225201	0.0114
INFLATION	-0.112288	0.112108	-0.214045	0.0740
CYCLICAL_OUTPUT	-1.214405	1.321405	-1.223154	0.0045
R-squared	0.075779	Mean dependent var		0.133311
Adjusted R-squared	0.058471	S.D. dependent var		0.075401
S.E. of regression	0.073163	Akaike info criterion		-2.370517
Sum squared resid	1.429210	Schwarz criterion		-2.291188
Log likelihood	329.5755	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.338672
F-statistic	4.378383	Durbin-Watson stat		0.849386
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000756			

Source: E - View 10Output

The coefficient estimates indicate that Capital base is positively related to the Return on Asset, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.0573, t-stat = 1.966, $p = 0.040 < 0.05$). Liquidity is though positively related to the Return on Asset; however, the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.061, t-stat = 1.120, $p = 0.264 > 0.05$). The coefficient estimates indicate that bank size is positively related to the Return on Asset, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.065, t-stat = 2.369, $p = 0.018 < 0.05$). Operational efficiency is positively related to the Return on Asset, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.009, t-stat = 2.871, $p = 0.004 < 0.05$). Credit risk negatively related to the Return on Asset, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.001, t-stat = -0.914, $p = 0.361 > 0.05$).

Table 5 further shows that the coefficient estimates indicate that market concentration is positively related to the Return on Asset, the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.324, t-stat = 1.225, $p = 0.011 < 0.05$). cyclical output (especially during economic recession) is negatively related to the Return on

Asset, and the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = -1.214, t-stat = -0.22, p = 0.004 < 0.05). Inflation negatively relate to the Return on Asset, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.112, t-stat = -0.21, p = 0.074 > 0.05).

The p 0.05 < 0.040, 0.001, 0.004, 0.011, 0.004, p 0.05 > 0.263,0.361, and 0.074, we hereby conclude that capital base has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Liquidity has a positive but insignificant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank size has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Operational Efficiency has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; and credit risk has negative but insignificant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria, Inflation and economic recession has negative impact on profitability of banks.

Table 6

Dependent Variable: ROE
Method: Panel Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.144933	0.152788	0.948586	0.3965
CAPITAL_BASE	0.046805	0.104212	1.449133	0.0066
LIQUITY	0.134796	0.342883	0.393124	0.7143
BANK_SIZE	0.025180	0.031292	1.804700	0.0061
OPERATIONAL_EFFICIEN CY	0.101997	0.105398	1.967735	0.0080
CREDIT_RISK	-0.394659	0.414182	-0.952864	0.3946
MARKET_CONCENTRATI ON	1.96E-05	3.59E-05	1.545521	0.0044
INFLATION	-0.001288	0.000608	-0.116745	0.1017
CYCLICAL_OUTPUT	-5.88E-05	3.69E-05	-1.591454	0.0067
R-squared	0.954039	Mean dependent var		0.290000
Adjusted R-squared	0.862117	S.D. dependent var		0.071764
S.E. of regression	0.026648	Akaike info criterion		-4.206273
Sum squared resid	0.002840	Schwarz criterion		-3.815155
Log likelihood	36.34078	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.286666
F-statistic	10.37882	Durbin-Watson stat		2.900910
Prob(F-statistic)	0.019248			

Source: E - View 10 Output.

Table 6 shows the coefficient estimates indicate that capital base is positively related to the Return on Equity, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.047, t-stat = 1.449, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$). Liquidity is though positively related to the Return on Equity; however, the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.134, t-stat = 0.393, $p = 0.714 > 0.05$). The coefficient estimates indicate that bank size is positively related to the Return on Equity, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.025, t-stat = 1.801, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$). Operational efficiency is positively related to the Return on Equity, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.101, t-stat = 1.968, $p = 0.008 < 0.05$). Credit risk negatively related to the Return on Equity, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.0394, t-stat = -0.953, $p = 0.395 > 0.05$).

Table 6 further shows that the coefficient estimates indicate that market concentration is positively related to the Return on Equity, the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 1.96, t-stat = 1.545, $p = 0.004 < 0.05$). cyclical output (especially during economic recession) is negatively related to the Return on Equity, and the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = -5.88, t-stat = -1.591, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$). Inflation negatively relate to the Return on Equity, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.001, t-stat = -0.112, $p = 0.102 > 0.05$).

The $p < 0.05 < 0.006, 0.006, 0.008, 0.004, 0.006; p > 0.714, 0.394, \text{ and } 0.101$, we hereby conclude that capital base has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Liquidity has a positive but insignificant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank size has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Operational Efficiency has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; and credit risk has negative but insignificant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria, inflation and economic recession has negative impact on profitability of banks.

Table 7

Dependent Variable: NIM

Method: Panel Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.436114	0.136563	3.193508	0.0331
CAPITAL_BASE	0.005752	0.093145	1.061750	0.0037
LIQUITY	0.370123	0.306470	1.207698	0.0037
BANK_SIZE	1.001204	0.027969	1.043049	0.0047
OPERATIONAL_EFFICIENCY	1.028210	0.094205	1.299450	0.0045
CREDIT_RISK	-0.192272	0.370197	-0.519379	0.6309
MARKET_CONCENTRATION	1.41E-05	3.21E-05	1.438444	0.0014

INFLATION	0.000241	0.000544	0.442830	0.6808
CYCLICAL_OUTPUT	6.24E-06	3.30E-05	0.189039	0.8593
R-squared	0.577381	Mean dependent var	0.358462	
Adjusted R-squared	-0.267857	S.D. dependent var	0.021153	
S.E. of regression	0.023818	Akaike info criterion	-4.430812	
Sum squared resid	0.002269	Schwarz criterion	-4.039693	
Log likelihood	37.80028	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-4.511204	
F-statistic	0.683099	Durbin-Watson stat	1.994982	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000995			

Source: E - View 10 Output.

Table 7 shows the coefficient estimates indicate that capital base is positively related to the net interest margin, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.006, t-stat = 1.062, $p = 0.003 < 0.05$). Liquidity is positively related to the interest margin, the relationship is statistically significant at 5% level of significant (Coef = 0.370, t-stat = 1.208, $p = 0.007 > 0.05$). The coefficient estimates indicate that bank size is positively related to the interest margin, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 1.001, t-stat = 1.043, $p = 0.005 < 0.05$). Operational efficiency is positively related to the interest margin, and that the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 1.028, t-stat = 1.299, $p = 0.005 < 0.05$). Credit risk negatively related to the interest margin, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.192, t-stat = -0.519, $p = 0.604 > 0.05$).

Table 7 further shows that the coefficient estimates indicate that market concentration is positively related to the interest margin, the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = 1.421, t-stat = 1.438, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$). Cyclical output (economic regression) is negatively related to the interest margin, and the relationship is statistically significant at conventional levels of 5% level of significant (Coef = -6.241, t-stat = -1.189, $p = 0.040 < 0.05$). Inflation negatively impact on interest margin, though the relationship is statistically insignificant at 5% level of significant (Coef = -0.000, t-stat = -0.443, $p = 0.681 > 0.05$).

The study hereby conclude that capital base has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Liquidity has a positive and significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank size has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Bank Operational Efficiency has a positive significant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria; and credit risk has negative but insignificant impact on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria, inflation and economic recession has negative impact on profitability of banks.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between capital base and profitability of banks

There is a positive relationship between capital base and all three proxies of profitability used which is also significant at 5% level of significance. This suggests that increases in capital base will have a significantly positive impact on banks profit. This finding is consistent with the findings of Berger and Mester (1997). Also, the result also conforms to the findings of Aburime (2008) and Aburime&Uche (2006) and Vong& Chan (2013) which found capital base to be a significant determinant of bank profit. On the contrary, the result contradicts those of Flamini *et al* (2009) and Ongore&Kusa (2013).

Relationship between bank size and profitability of banks

This results show that bank size has a significant impact on profitability in all three proxies used also being positive. That is to say as bank size increases so does profitability. This result is in line with findings by Bikker&Hu (2002) as well as Goddard *et al* (2004) but contrary to findings by Berger *et al* (1997) and Heffernan &Fu (2008) and Aremu, Ekpo& Mustapha (2013).

Relationship between liquidity and profitability of banks

This results show that while there is a positive relationship between the proxy of liquidity used here to profitability in all three measurements i.e. (ROA, ROE & NIM) it is however only significant in NIM. The positive relationship with Profitability supports the findings of Bourke (1989) and Hoffmann (2011) who found a positive relationship for ROE While Pasiouras&Kosmidou (2007) and Aremu *et al* (2013) and Osuagwu (2014) agree to the negative relationship of liquidity with profitability

Relationship between operational efficiency and profitability of banks

There is a positive and significant relationship between operational efficiency and profitability of banks in Nigeria in all three proxies used. This shows its importance to the industry as a very efficient use of resources looks to yield higher profitability. This result is consistent with findings of Akinkunmi (2017) and Osuagwu (2014).

Relationship between credit risk and profitability of banks

This results show that the credit risk proxied by NPL ratio has no significant impact on profitability in all three instances with a negative relationship. This result is consistent with the finding in Athanasoglou, *et al.* (2006) and Osuagwu (2014), but contradicts the result in Goddard (2004) for European banks.

Relationship between market concentration and profitability of banks

In this study, the market variable was represented by hhi which is a measure of banking industry concentration in this study and is significant to estimating the changes in return on assets. The relationship is positive which signifies that as bank concentration is increasing, profitability is increasing. This result is in line with the finding in Flamini *et al.* (2009) for the banking system in sub-Saharan Africa, and Hoffman (2011).

Relationship between inflation and profitability of banks

The finding of this study reveals that inflation has no significant effect on profitability of banks in Nigeria. This is also in line with findings by Krakah&Ameyaw (2010) and Aremu *et al* (2013) and contrary to the findings of Vong& Chan (2013).

Relationship between cyclical output and profitability of banks

In this study cyclical output proxied by real GDP growth rate had a negative and significant relationship to profitability using ROE and ROA, but had a positive and insignificant relationship to NIM. However due to the significant relationship to ROA and ROE, it can be concluded that cyclical output is a determinant of bank profitability. This is in line with findings of Dietrich and Wanzenried (2011). This is contrary to findings of Akinkunmi (2017) and Aremu et al (2013).

CONCLUSION

This study was targeted at establishing some determinants of banks' profitability in Nigeria using an annual panel dataset for the time period of (2006-2018). The dependent variable was profitability measured with three different proxies namely Return on assets, return on equity and net interest margin. While the independent variables were bank's size, capital base, liquidity, credit risk, and efficiency in the bank's operations which made up the bank specific determinants and market concentration, cyclical output and inflation which made up the macro-economic determinants. The study revealed that capital base, bank size operational efficiency, market concentration and liquidity have a positive relationship with ROA which is significant except for liquidity, while credit risk, inflation and cyclical output have a negative relationship to ROA with cyclical output being significant.

In regards to ROE, capital base, bank size operational efficiency, market concentration and liquidity a positively related with significant relationship in all of them except for liquidity, while credit risk, inflation and cyclical output are negatively related to ROE with significant relationship in only cyclical output.

Lastly, all independent variables used except for credit risk are positively related to NIM but with cyclical output representing economic recession and inflation being insignificant. Also credit risk has an insignificant relationship to the dependent variable.

DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

This study employed ordinary least square (OLS) panel data regression technique to ascertain the determinants of bank profitability. To contribute to the literature on bank performance and profitability, the Random Effect (RE) and Fixed Effect variants of panel data should be utilised to evaluate and confirm the relationship between the variables employed in this study. More so, the independent variables can be lagged to assess the relationship between the variables.

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